

THE MAIN CATEGORIES OF THE SCIENCE OF PEDAGOGY

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Annotation. This article discusses the main categories of the science of pedagogy.

Keywords: pedagogy, socio-economic, relationship, tool.

ОСНОВНЫЕ КАТЕГОРИИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ НАУКИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются основные категории педагогической науки.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, социально-экономические отношения, инструмент.

In the 21st century, it is increasingly evident that human intelligence and spirituality are the main coordinating, developing factors and tools in the development of socio-economic relations. Therefore, humanism is the main principle of building a legal, democratic state, and a strong civil society on the basis of a market economy.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" declared education a priority in the field of social development of our state, which imposed great responsibility and lofty tasks on the pedagogical science. Our very rich scientific, spiritual, cultural, and religious heritage began to be restored. Only an independent science has its own subject and methodological foundations.

In particular, pedagogy was formed as a science and has its own subject. Like other sciences, pedagogy emerged as a science, first of all based on the demands and needs of society.

Therefore, the educational process should be considered an integral part of social life.

Because it is difficult to imagine society and its development without educational work.

The term pedagogy is ancient and comes from the Greek word "paedagogos", which means "child-leader". According to historical sources, in ancient Greece, a tutor who took his masters' children for a walk and took care of them "pedagogue" ("child guide"). Later, this concept was used in a broader sense and began to be applied to specialists with specialized knowledge. At the same time, those involved in educational work began to stand out as patrons of the profession.

The activities of scholars in the field of education and the appropriate use of their accumulated experience led to the emergence of the discipline of PEDAGOGY. From the first days of our independence, many innovations and positive changes related to universal human processes have occurred in our political, social, cultural, spiritual and scientific life. "The most important thing is that the thinking and worldview of a person and a citizen are changing, their political and social consciousness, their general level are constantly growing,"¹ - emphasizes our First President I.A. Karimov. Pedagogy is a unique discipline not only in terms of its subject of study, but also in terms of its historical development. The teachings of the "Avesta", the lessons of the "Holy Quran", the great masters of the science of hadith such as Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari (810-970), Abu Isa Muhammad ibn Isa at-Tirmidhi (824-892) made a great contribution to the educational process and laid the foundation for the formation of pedagogy.

Their pedagogical views have taken a worthy place in the golden pages of history. Each discipline has its own basic concepts that arise from its content and essence, serve to illuminate its main aspects and are most often used.

Similarly, the discipline of pedagogy also has its own main categories. Category - (Greek: category - "indication", "evidence", "all") is a basic concept in pedagogy that reflects the characteristics, essence and content of pedagogical processes, the relationship between the individual and society, the individual and the group, the individual and the community, education and upbringing, spiritual-enlightenment, moral-aesthetic, economic-ecological, etc.

The category arose on the basis of the historical development of cognitive processes and the experience of society. Through categories, a person studies being, the environment, events occurring in social life. One of these and the main one is the term "Pedagogy". (It comes from the Greek words "paydagogos", meaning "child" and "agogein" - to lead). The explanation for this is as follows: In the III-I centuries BC, ancient Greece, a slave who fed his child, took him for a walk, and played with him in nature was called a "pedagogue." Today, the word "pedagogue" has acquired a broad, new meaning. Another important concept of pedagogy is the word "didactyly." In ancient Greece, a person who taught a slave's child at school was called a "didactyly." "Didactics" comes from the Greek word "didaktikos," which means "to teach," "to teach," and "to give knowledge." The ancient Greeks used the terms "didasko" for teaching, "didaskal" for a teacher, and "didascale" for a student. However, the term "didactics" has moved far from its original meaning. Now the scope and content of these concepts have become much richer and expanded, covering not only the activities of the teacher, but also the activities of the student. The main categories of pedagogy include education, upbringing, information, development, pedagogical activity, pedagogical process, knowledge, teaching, educational and upbringing methods, principles, etc. We also call them pedagogical concepts.

Upbringing is the systematic influence of the educator on the psyche of the students in order to instill the desired qualities in their minds. Since the term "upbringing" is considered a broad concept in world pedagogy, there are various theories about its essence.

The most common tendency is to understand upbringing as a process of influence of adults (teachers, tutors and parents) on children. This implies, of course, influence in accordance with ideals, goals, tasks, norms and requirements that adults consider correct and evaluate. Such an understanding of upbringing is closer to reality, but it is one-sided and reflects only a certain part of this process. In this definition of upbringing, the child is considered only as an object on which the influence of adults is directed. While pedagogy also involves the upbringing of initiative and independent individuals, it gives the pupil the role of an active subject in the pedagogical process.

The image formed by imagining a person's self, their behavioral characteristics, and their position in society is called the "I" image, and its adequacy and closeness to reality determine a person's social position in society and are considered criteria for perfection.

The socio-psychological significance of the "I" image is that it is one of the factors of a person's upbringing and the level of his upbringing. From this perspective, "... upbringing can be defined as the process of forming a person's ideas about himself and his qualities." Therefore, the more clearly and correctly each person understands and imagines himself, his identity, the less likely he is to act contrary to the moral norms of society. Abdullah Avloni, in his work "Turkish Rose or Morality," emphasized the importance of upbringing in human development, saying, "The Almighty created people with talents and abilities in their original creation, able to distinguish between good and evil, benefit and harm, white and black. However, this ability in a person can be perfected through upbringing. If a child is well-educated, protected from bad behavior, and grows up accustomed to good behavior, he will become a happy person.

If he grows up without education and with bad morals, he will become an ignorant, ignorant, disgraceful person who does not listen to advice and does all kinds of bad things,” he emphasizes. Therefore, today, pedagogical diagnostics and correction play an important role in researching and finding solutions to the problems of pedagogical theory and practice. Education is a process that equips students with knowledge, skills, and competencies, which develops cognitive abilities and shapes their worldview, carried out under the guidance of specially trained people. Information is a set of knowledge obtained and systematized as a result of education and upbringing, acquired skills, and competencies, and formed worldviews. Pedagogical activity is a special type of socially necessary work of adults, which is a rational preparation of the younger generation for life in accordance with such goals as aesthetic, moral, political, economic. The pedagogical process is the self-development of the child, organized and enriched in content under the influence of the pedagogical activity of the teacher, aimed at a certain goal, and as a result of the guiding and leading role of the educator. No science can achieve perfection in isolation. It is enriched in content in connection with other sciences, using their achievements. Similarly, the science of pedagogy relies on the knowledge created by humanity and information about the future. It is based on information about the laws of the development of nature and society, and it itself, developing as a social science, serves the social development of man.

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